

VOL. 7, 2024

ISSN 1473-8376

JOURNAL OF
**THE HOSPITALITY, LEISURE,
SPORT & TOURISM
NETWORK**

HIGHER EDUCATION ACADEMY, UK

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TEACHING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE TO NON- PHILOLOGY STUDENTS¹

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Abstract. Modern educational standards require the training of high-level qualified person who can freely use foreign languages in both social and daily communication situations within the scope of specialization and competitive in the international labor market. This criterion, which must be fulfilled by higher educational institutions, often creates difficulties for students of non-philological specialization. These difficulties appear in different forms, didactically and methodologically. The difficulty in teaching English is related to teaching grammar in these areas. This article discusses the features of teaching grammatical competence to non-linguistic students.

Keywords: competence, grammar, grammatical competence, ESP, non-linguistic students.

Introduction. In today's rapidly developing global community, modern knowledge and skills is crucial for active, initiative-driven participation. For any country pursuing an open policy and seeking global recognition and stability, it is essential for young professionals to have profound knowledge and critical thinking skills. Achieving a well-rounded potential and a contemporary worldview is greatly supported by mastering foreign languages and acquiring effective communication skills. The foundation of mastering a foreign language lies in understanding its internal structure and grammar. Teaching grammar to students in non-linguistic disciplines differs significantly from the approach taken with linguistics-focused students. For non-linguistic fields, English is taught as a second language with a focus on specific objectives, known as ESP (English for Specific Purposes).

What is the competence? In linguistics, the term "competence" was introduced by Noam Chomsky (1965) in the 1960s alongside the concept of "linguistic competence"

¹ **Cite as:** Ganiyeva, D. (2024). Specific Features of Teaching Grammatical Competence to Non-Philology Students. The Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Network, 7, pp. 14-21. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14510308

referring to knowledge of grammar and language structure, which enables individuals to produce and understand language. According to Spolsky (1990), “competence” reflects not just how much knowledge a person has about language, but rather how they use it. A linguistic individual’s ability to apply their acquired knowledge, skills, and expertise in language in practical communication situations, i.e., their ability to engage in interaction, reveals the primary function of competence. According to Chesi(2012), “competence” is considered a generative procedure, motivating a native speaker to form and recognize an infinite number of grammatical sentences within their language. In other words, competence provides every language user with an unconscious ability to utilize the intrinsic capacities of their language.

According to Vitello and Greatorex (2021), from an educational perspective, competence has three main practical purposes, which are as follows:

- Firstly, it helps explain how people learn languages effectively.
- Secondly, the concept of competence, defined in an integrated and comprehensive way, prompts us to think about the various factors necessary for our activities (such as knowledge, skills, and abilities) and how these integrate with each other, enabling learners to work successfully in a specific field.
- Thirdly, the concept of competence holds educational value because it can be applied widely. Competence is not confined to any particular national education system or tradition, is not tailored to any specific subject area or age group, and is not limited to any specific stage of education or learning.

The concept of grammar. Around 2,500 years ago, foreign language instruction was closely tied to grammar teaching. However, in the 1970s, scholars who introduced a communicative approach to language teaching shifted grammar instruction from an “autonomous” position, reclassifying it as an integral component of communicative competence. No language in the world lacks grammatical structure, each language possesses its own unique structural composition. Grammar encompasses the rules for structuring words and sentences, ranging from simple to complex, and informs us on how words and sentences are

constructed to express ideas. Its primary function is to study the various parts of speech and their roles in detail.

A lack of deep grammatical knowledge limits a language learner's capabilities. Grammar knowledge represents the first essential stage in learning a foreign language as a second language. Mastering the grammatical structure of a language is critical for developing the four language skills listening comprehension, speaking, reading comprehension, and writing which are fundamental for communication in that language. Without understanding the grammatical framework of a language, effective communication becomes difficult and inefficient. Therefore, mastering a language is essentially synonymous with mastering its grammar.

The term "grammar" is often used in linguistics (knowledge about language) and, when applied in language teaching methodology, there is a common misconception that it carries the same meaning in both contexts. However, definitions of "grammar" vary due to different approaches to its teaching, making it challenging to provide a universally accepted definition. For this reason, let's examine several definitions provided by scholars.

The term "grammar" is derived from the Ancient Greek words "grammatike" and "gramma," meaning "letter" or "writing." In linguistics, grammar refers to the study of the structural rules governing the formation of words, phrases, and sentences in a language. From a linguistic perspective, "grammar" is the field that explores the internal structure of a language. According to the definition given in Cambridge Dictionary, "grammar is the study or use of rules that govern how words change form and combine with other words to convey meaning". This definition implies the necessity of studying grammatical rules and their application in expressing meaning. In the book "Chet tilini o'qitish metodikasi" (Methodology of Teaching foreign languages), J.Jalolov (2012) provides a specific definition of the term "grammar". He explains that the term can be confined to two concepts:

- 1) The grammatical aspect of speech-grammatical phenomena encountered in speaking, listening, reading, and writing (e.g., examples of speech; verb forms; articles).

- 2) Abstract concepts describing linguistic phenomena (e.g., the subject occupies the first position in a sentence; in

a foreign language, a certain suffix is added to form the plural of a noun from its singular form).

According to M.Swan (2002), “Knowing how to use specific structures and how to construct them leads to the successful application of common types of meaning in communication. Without these structures, it becomes difficult to form detailed sentences”. Therefore, grammatical structures prevent misinterpretation of meaning, allowing the speaker to fully convey the intended message.

Grammatical competence. The term “grammatical competence” was generally introduced by N.Chomsky as a component of linguistic competence. Grammatical competence has been the subject of numerous research studies, and when explored by scholars, the following definitions have been provided for the term grammatical competence.

Grammatical competence refers to the speaker’s ability to intuitively use and apply grammatical knowledge, enabling them to use and understand language effectively. It encompasses the ability to acquire knowledge about vocabulary, morphology, syntax, semantics, and more. According to A. Rosales (2019), “grammatical competence” is the mastery of linguistic codes and the ability to understand the morphological and syntactic features of language, allowing for the effective use of these features in encoding and decoding words and sentences. According to H.Kitura and I.Prokop (2023), “grammatical competence” involves the ability to correctly use grammatical forms in English while adhering to grammatical rules and standards. It encompasses the capacity to express and understand ideas, focusing not on merely recalling and reproducing ready-made templates, but rather on recognizing and constructing phrases based on clear principles. In the research on developing grammatical competence, T. Berkutova defines “grammatical competence” as the ability to understand the grammatical structure of others’ speech based on a dynamic and complex interplay of grammatical knowledge and essential skills. This competence also includes the precise grammatical construction of one’s spoken and written expressions. R.Milrud (2014), on the other hand, concludes that grammatical competence encompasses essential language skills and grammatical knowledge (rules) that allow students to construct correct sentences, understand them,

check for grammatical errors, make judgments about correct and incorrect linguistic forms, and complete tasks that assess language proficiency.

According to K. Singman (1997), grammatical competence is the ability to skillfully master linguistic codes, including speech sounds, words, sentence structure, and spelling. This competence plays a crucial role in developing learners' communicative competence.

Grammatical competence involves the ability to use grammatical resources of the language and to understand and apply the language effectively. It also entails knowledge of theoretical and practical grammatical rules that aid in understanding correctly structured sentences. This competence helps speakers accurately and swiftly comprehend and use structures in English.

Teaching english grammar competence to non-linguistic students. In teaching English to students in non-philological fields, numerous misunderstandings often arise regarding the role of grammar. This is because these programs typically focus on English for Specific Purposes (ESP), which does not emphasize developing grammatical competence, leading to grammatical challenges that hinder students' productive and receptive skills. The more these grammatical deficiencies are addressed, the greater the improvement in students' overall English proficiency.

A lack of grammatical knowledge can obstruct comprehension, particularly in understanding meaning, grasping the relationship between form and context, and interpreting meaning within a sentence. Key areas often lacking include understanding verb forms, tense and aspect, modals, logical connectors, compound nouns, and expressions conveying cause and effect.

In communication, students often encounter significant issues due to grammatical gaps, particularly when preparing written assignments or oral presentations. As a solution to these challenges, it is recommended to teach both grammatical forms and their contextual applications, tailored to the students' specific professional needs.

T. Augustina(2014) emphasizes two key considerations in selecting instructional materials for teaching English to students in non-philological fields: the language system and language use. The language system

includes grammatical structure and vocabulary. Grammatical structure and vocabulary are essential, as they play a central role in scientific and technical written language. An analysis of scientific and technical texts reveals that the grammatical structures used differ from those in general English texts, with a notably higher use of passive voice verb forms in these specialized texts.

Teaching grammatical competence in English to students in non-philological fields requires a specialized approach tailored to their specific language needs and contexts. This approach includes several key features:

1. **Contextualization.** Grammatical knowledge is integrated into the context of the students' specific field of study. For example, legal studies use grammatical structures distinct from those in technical fields.1. Contextualization. In this, grammatical knowledge is included in the context of a special field of education.

2. **Relevance.** Grammar instruction should be directly linked to the students' specific objectives, such as delivering presentations, writing broadcast reports, or drafting industry-specific documents.

3. **Practical Application** is placed on using grammatical structures in real-world situations relevant to the students' disciplines. This involves activities and tasks such as role-playing or giving presentations that encourage practical use of grammar.

4. **Integrated Teaching.** Instead of teaching grammar in isolation, it is integrated with other language skills, such as writing, listening, reading, and speaking, within the context of the students' field of study.

5. **Communicative Grammar.** Grammar is taught as a tool for effective communication. Students learn how different grammatical choices can alter meaning and impact in the context of their specific fields.

6. **Correction and Feedback.** When using grammar in specialized contexts, feedback is provided in a way that helps students understand their errors without demotivating them, thus enhancing the effectiveness of grammar acquisition.

7. **Assessment.** Grammatical competence is assessed through tasks that reflect real-world scenarios students may encounter in their professional fields, ensuring relevance and practical application.

The following goals are set in the teaching of grammatical competence to students of the non-philological direction:

- 1) Formation of language-specific mechanisms;
- 2) Formation of grammatical knowledge and skills;
- 3) Applying learned grammatical knowledge and structure in practice;
- 4) Introducing the latest information on grammar;
- 5) To develop the ability to think in English in the context of the taught subjects.

Conclusion. Foreign language learning takes long journey. In order to shorten this journey, selecting proper curriculum and materials are key factors that assist language learners to enhance language proficiency. However, it is essential to take into consideration of students' needs for learning english! English for specific purposes also known ESP is the branch of EFL (english as a foreign language) was introduced to typical aims of students. Nevertheless, problems of language acquisition are still encountered in non-philological specialities. One of the main barriers is lack of grammar knowledge. Awareness of the specific features of gramatical competence is such an important farctor to overcome such barriers. This featutes include: contextualization, relevance,integrating, teaching communicatively, feedback and assessment.

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